

Interactions Afforded by Mobile Telepresence Robots in Health Care Settings

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Abstract. Mobile telepresence robots (MTRs) allow communication and mobility to interact from a distant location. In health care settings, these robots are used to enhance interactions between physicians, patients, and family members. MTRs can thus be effective in improving quality and efficiency in health care; however, the interactions that MTRs afford need to be studied to address issues related to their design, development, and implementation in line with the physical affordance space by looking not only at the features but also at the relationships they create. Therefore, this study aims to identify the types of interactions offered by two different types of MTRs in health care settings, the relevance of each interaction depending on the type of health care setting, and the perceived differences between the two MTRs. Empirical data were collected in Spain, in two hospitals, a nursing home and with professionals from private clinics. With a qualitative approach, the main data source were 25 semi-structured interviews with informants that used CLARC and GoBe tests in situ and video recorded as stimulus. Additionally, observations, two focus groups and archival data were collected. Findings show two types of interactions: displacement and simultaneity. Furthermore, perceived differences related to the appearance of the two MTRs result in different evoked feelings that are either appropriate or inappropriate depending on the type of patient. This study improves the understanding of how to design, develop, and implement MTRs in health care settings by expanding knowledge on the proper fit between type of interaction and setting.

Keywords: Mobile Telepresence Robots · Human-Robot Interaction · Health Care

1 Introduction

As a result of their use in health care settings, robots may impact patients' health positively by facilitating access and speed of caregiving tasks [1]. Mobile telepresence robots (MTRs) are a type of robot that can be controlled remotely by users to interact with local informants [2]. Therefore, MTRs that are implemented and used in health

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care settings may enable remote interactions between health care workers, patients, and family members while supporting physical presence [3]. MTRs may thus provide emotional and physical support [4] in health care settings by allowing social interaction and by enabling in situ mobility for remote users. For example, telepresence can promote well-being, increase self-esteem and reduce loneliness in the elderly [5]. In situations such as infectious disease outbreaks, telepresence can help alleviate the negative effects of social distancing on the elderly and patients [6]. Furthermore, healthcare processes can be improved in terms of efficiency because robots can facilitate access and speed of care tasks, for example, with telemedicine practices. Even when the health sector measures performance mainly with the well-being of patients and not with the maximization of profits [7], the use of robots such as MTRs is relevant due to the benefits for effective performance.

1.1 Relational Approach for the Study of Interactions

MTRs can be effective in improving quality and efficiency in health care [1]; however, the interactions that emerge when health care staff, patients, and family members communicate through such robots need to be studied to address issues related to the design, development, and implementation of MTRs. The study of interactions provides an opportunity to address issues related to the design and development of robots in line with the physical affordance space by looking not only at the features but also at the relationships they create [8, 9]. Focusing on interactions will allow a relational approach to MTRs' design and development, which considers aspects of the social environment, context characteristics, users, stakeholders and robot features [10]. Therefore, this study aims to identify: (i) the types of interactions offered by two different types of MTRs in healthcare settings, (ii) the relevance of each interaction depending on the type of setting, and (iii) the perceived differences between the two MTRs. In doing so, the study contributes both theoretically and practically by providing insights to inform discussions among interdisciplinary teams and stakeholders who are researching, designing, developing, implementing, and using MTRs in health care settings.

2 Methodology

Data was collected from different sources of information and analyzed with the help of qualitative case study methodology, which is particularly appropriate for fields that are not mature [11, 12]. As part of a larger exploratory research that investigated the safety and effectiveness of MTRs in health care settings, test environments were created in which one or two different MTRs, CLARC and GoBe were tested. CLARC (see Fig. 1) has a humanoid form that includes a touch screen at the torso, a shotgun microphone, speakers, and a webcam developed by the University of Malaga and was, at the time, being tested in a nursing home located in Malaga, Spain. GoBe (see Fig. 2) is an MTR with a touch display, multiple cameras, speakers, and microphone developed by the Danish company Blue Ocean Robotics and was being tested in the nursing home and in two hospitals located in Seville, Spain. Moreover, the study included independent professionals working in private clinics in the south of Spain that were selected using snowball sampling.

Fig. 1. CLARC at the nursing home.

Fig. 2. GoBe at the nursing home.

2.1 Data Collection and Analysis

The first author visited the health care settings three to four times per week between April and May 2022 to collect primary and secondary data. While onsite, the researcher (i) observed daily health care practices, (ii) participated in the MTR tests, and (iii) conducted the interviews with staff. The main primary data source were 25 semi-structured interviews with health care staff working in the selected health care settings. Only interviews with private clinic informants were conducted via Zoom, where MTRs were presented via a video recording. The informants had various occupations, e.g., nurses, physiotherapists, psychologists, social workers, and psychiatrists. Each interview lasted between 20 to 30 min. The first part of the interview was related to the MTR being tested at the time to elucidate the health care staff's perspectives and then about the second MTR, which created the basis for comparison. Reflective notes were taken based on the onsite observations and the informal conversations.

The secondary data included two 40-min focus groups, one with four staff members and one with four residents, that were conducted in the nursing home as part of the larger assessment to evaluate the strengths and weaknesses of GoBe and CLARC. Other sources of secondary data were three media articles related to the MTR project at the nursing home and five emails exchanged between CLARC developers and the nursing home director. These sources provided insights about the perspectives of the nursing home residents and top management.

As we transcribed the interviews and collected the reflective field notes and secondary data transcripts, we followed a coding process that involved first-order concepts, second-order themes leading to aggregated dimensions. This process was done in NVivo to identify patterns, determine categories, analyze them, and interpret them in-depth [13]. Several strategies were employed in interpreting the data including constant comparison

and replication logic to find common topics between the cases and facilitate abstraction [11].

3 Findings and Discussion

3.1 The Types of Interactions

Displacement Interaction. This interaction type occurs when video calls between patients or nursing home residents and family members are handled by MTRs instead of health care staff. With CLARC, a family member can log into the system and choose a time slot for the call. With GoBe, they can connect immediately to start the video call. Hospital patients and nursing home residents may require communicating remotely with family members and thus health care workers must organize video calls, i.e., find a convenient time, hold the mobile device throughout the call and support in case of technical issues. This task became a challenge in the nursing home during the COVID-19 lockdown due to the larger number of residents compared to the number of employees. This resulted in health care staff abandoning their core caretaking tasks, which created a feeling of dissatisfaction. In a displacement interaction, health care staff are no longer organizing the patient-family member video call and may focus on job-related tasks. As illustrated by an informant “having that ability to make more video calls without taking time away from professionals [...] this way they are not limiting the work of the physiotherapist, the psychologist” (P17). Furthermore, the analysis showed that patients benefit from the privacy during the video calls with their families in the displacement interaction, given that there is no health care worker standing next to them to hold the device or assist.

Simultaneity Interaction. This interaction type takes place when health care staff connects to the MTR to communicate with patients or nursing home residents, e.g., a psychiatrist located in a capital city can connect remotely to an MTR situated in a rural area hospital to give consultation. Some informants mentioned that using MTRs for a first diagnosis could be very effective in emergency cases, and later they can proceed with the treatment in-person. MTRs add value in the emergency room (ER) because there are cases that need the assistance of different medical specialties that might not be physically present. There are some medical specialties such as physiotherapists that need to manipulate patients physically, however, the interviewees from this field of medicine mentioned that there is an opportunity for educating patients through a simultaneity interaction by showing them how to perform exercises and monitoring remotely. Additionally, using MTRs instead of other mobile devices may improve the diagnosis. As put by an informant, “it will give the health professionals behind it a vision they do not normally have during an emergency call, many factors could be seen (P11)”. Hospital nurses mentioned that using MTRs for communicating with patients that are in different rooms could help them avoid unnecessary movements and optimize work time given that they usually walk back and forth from the nursing station to the patient’s room to exchange a few words, which is sometimes perceived as unnecessary. MTRs can thus help healthcare staff add more value within their core tasks.

3.2 The Relevance of Each Interaction Depends on the Type of Health Care Setting

The identified types of interactions afforded by MTRs in health care settings are (i) displacement and (ii) simultaneity. Each interaction will bring different benefits to the quality and efficiency of healthcare depending on the context characteristics and stakeholders involved. Therefore, increasing the quality and effectiveness of health practices with MTRs may be easier if healthcare providers have a clear understanding of which types of interactions most appropriately fit the type of setting, whether it be a nursing home, hospital, or private clinic.

The Displacement Interaction is More Relevant in the Nursing Home. Informants from the nursing home appeared to be more disrupted by the burden of organizing video calls compared to hospital and private clinic interviewees. As some informants explained, elderly people are usually dependent on health care staff to communicate with their family members because they might not be familiar with technology or might be physically impaired. Therefore, the displacement interaction that emerges when MTRs can manage video calls independently appears to be highly relevant in nursing homes. On the other hand, this type of interaction is relevant in hospitals when patients who are isolated or physically disabled need to make video calls with family members. Some informants' opinion was that video calls to family members through an MTR may evoke a feeling of closeness that may contribute to the patient's wellbeing, which is perceived as highly relevant when they have been isolated. Finally, the informants from the private clinics mentioned that MTRs for displacement interactions add no value in outpatient clinics because patients receive treatment without staying there overnight.

The Simultaneity Interaction is More Helpful in Hospitals. Informants working in private clinics and nursing homes mentioned that this type of interaction is more useful in hospitals given that in private clinics and nursing homes the attention is usually face-to-face, characterized by being more personalized and well-planned than in hospitals, and thus in-person interactions are considered more appropriate for these health care settings. However, some informants mentioned that medical attention via MTRs could be done sporadically in private clinics and nursing homes only if the patient agrees in advance. On the other hand, informants working in hospitals argued that MTRs may be more useful in such settings than in nursing homes or private clinics because hospitals usually have a large number of patients, who are not always expected to come for consultation, and only a few health workers to assist them. Therefore, the use of MTR could help alleviate the workload of local doctors by facilitating mobile telepresence to other health professionals who are not present in hospitals but have time to see patients, resulting in a more effective health care service. Table 1 summarizes the reasons for the relevance of each interaction in nursing homes, hospitals, and private clinics.

3.3 Perceived Differences Between the MTRs

The main perceived difference between GoBe and CLARC is related to their appearance, which in turn created a difference in the evoked feelings. To illustrate, while CLARC is perceived as "informal" and "toy-like", GoBe is perceived as "sophisticated", and "more

Table 1. Relevance of each interaction in each case.

Case	Displacement Interaction	Simultaneity Interaction
Nursing Home	High Relevance Elderly people are dependent on health care staff to use mobile devices for video calls	Low Relevance Medical attention is well-planned and personalized, and thus considered more appropriate in-person
Hospital #1 and #2	Medium Relevance Physically impaired or isolated patients depend on health care staff to use mobile devices for video calls	High Relevance Reaching remote patients who need urgent medical attention improves health care effectiveness
Private Clinics	Low Relevance Patients usually receive treatment without staying there overnight	Low Relevance Medical attention is well-planned and personalized, and thus considered more appropriate in-person

functional”. The appearance of each MTR makes it more appropriate for some patients and less appropriate for others. As put by an informant, “For mental health patients, CLARC can trigger fear or hallucinations, that is why I think the other [GoBe] is more neutral” (P12). Observations revealed that the nursing home residents called CLARC by the name “Felipe” and had conversations with the MTR when turned off, while no conversations were observed with GoBe. Thus, CLARC may evoke a feeling of presence of an ascribed identity, while GoBe may be better at evoking a feeling of closeness, as if the person operating the MTR is present in the room, “It gives the feeling of company, being tall, because it is the height of a person, it seems to me that it can be of great help for some people, especially in isolation” (P22). “It seems that it is the family member who approaches [the resident], then I think it is easier for them to recognize them” (P5). In the nursing home, GoBe’s screen size resulted an advantage compared to CLARC’s, given that elderly people might be visually impaired. However, some informants believed that CLARC may be more beneficial for elderly people because it has a familiar form, “For older patients perhaps a robot in human form would be more friendly [...], for young patients who are more used to technology, I think the screen would be good” (P13).

3.4 Considerations for the Design, Development, and Implementation of MTRs in Health Care Settings

Design and Development Implications. Some participants proposed new features or ways in which both MTRs could be improved to contribute more effectively to the quality and effectiveness of health care. The proposals did not distinguish between the MTRs but, rather, addressed them in general. Related to the hardware, some participants mentioned the relevance of having a button to call staff when assistance is needed, as well as an emergency button to turn off the MTR immediately. Also, hospital nurses preferred the MTRs to have a space to carry objects that patients may need, e.g., tissues. As for

the software, input from interviewees and observations revealed that MTRs should be able to detect objects while navigating to avoid accidents or an autonomous navigation mode, mainly in the nursing home, because residents are usually walking around with no supervision. Also, some clinicians would like to share relevant information through the screen with the patients during remote consultations, similar to sharing their screens with other tools such as Zoom.

Effective Implementation of MTRs in Health Care Settings. For an effective implementation of MTRs in health care settings, the fit between type of interaction and setting should be considered. This requires taking into account the relevance of each interaction depending on the type of health care setting, which implies analyzing what a certain group of users and stakeholders may require. For instance, a nursing home may highly benefit from a displacement interaction because patients are dependent on health care workers to communicate, while hospitals may benefit more from a simultaneity interaction because health care staff's workload may be decreased if remote clinicians join with the MTRs to assist onsite patients. Private clinics might not be the most appropriate setting for MTRs interactions, as can be seen in Table 1. Moreover, choosing GoBe or CLARC for a given health care setting may depend on whether patients should be attached to the MTR or not. Findings showed that patients may build an affective relationship with CLARC due to the humanoid form, whereas GoBe has a neutral form that is less likely to trigger such social reactions.

4 Conclusion

This study covers implications for the design, development, and implementation of MTRs in health care settings by looking not only at the features but also at the relationships created with patients, nursing home residents, health workers and family members. It also highlights the relevance of identifying a suitable fit between the type of interaction and the type of health care setting to increase the benefits of implementing MTRs in such settings. Future research may examine the effects of using MTRs in health care settings with particular medical specialties and types of patients to understand differences and best practices.

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References

1. Sætra, H.S.: The foundations of a policy for the use of social robots in care. *Technol. Soc.* **63**, 101383 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techsoc.2020.101383>

2. Lee, M.K., Takayama, L.: “Now, i have a body”: uses and social norms for mobile remote presence in the workplace. In: Proceedings of the SIGCHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems, pp. 33–42. ACM, Vancouver BC Canada (2011). <https://doi.org/10.1145/1978942.1978950>
3. Koceski, S., Koceska, N.: Evaluation of an assistive telepresence robot for elderly healthcare. *J. Med. Syst.* **40**(5), 1–7 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10916-016-0481-x>
4. Sparrow, R., Sparrow, L.: In the hands of machines? the future of aged care. *Mind. Mach.* **16**, 141–161 (2006). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11023-006-9030-6>
5. Cesta, A., Cortellesa, G., Orlandini, A., Tiberio, L.: Long-term evaluation of a telepresence robot for the elderly: methodology and ecological case study. *Int. J. Soc. Robot.* **8**(3), 421–441 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12369-016-0337-z>
6. Scassellati, B., Vázquez, M.: The potential of socially assistive robots during infectious disease outbreaks. *Sci. Robot.* **5**, eabc9014 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1126/scirobotics.abc9014>
7. Kim, R.H., Gaukler, G.M., Lee, C.W.: Improving healthcare quality: a technological and managerial innovation perspective. *Technol. Forecast. Soc. Chang.* **113**, 373–378 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2016.09.012>
8. Fischer, K., et al.: Integrative Social Robotics Hands-on. *IS.* **21**, 145–185 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1075/is.18058.fis>
9. Seibt, J., Flensburg Damholdt, M., Vestergaard, C.: Integrative social robotics, value-driven design, and transdisciplinarity. *IS.* **21**, 111–144 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1075/is.18061.sei>
10. Prescott, T.J., Robillard, J.M.: Designing Socially-Assistive Robots. ICCHP-AAATE 2022 Open Access Compendium “Assistive Technology. Accessibility, 8 pages (2022). <https://doi.org/10.35011/ICCHP-AAATE22-P2-36>
11. Eisenhardt, K.M.: Building theories from case study research. *Acad. Manag. Rev.* **14**, 532 (1989). <https://doi.org/10.2307/258557>
12. Yin, R.K.: Case study research: design and methods. Sage Publications, Los Angeles, Calif (2009)
13. Gioia, D.A., Corley, K.G., Hamilton, A.L.: Seeking qualitative rigor in inductive research: notes on the gioia methodology. *Organ. Res. Methods* **16**, 15–31 (2013). <https://doi.org/10.1177/1094428112452151>

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